

A Quantitative Methodology to Support Local Governments in Climate Change Adaptation and Mitigation Actions

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Abstract. Tackling climate change is a multidisciplinary process, which affects all aspects of government, on a local, regional and national scale. Local governments are publishing and using data related to climate change response and evidence-based actions, enabling the use of transparent and data-driven solutions. It is essential to provide user-friendly data-driven methodologies and tools in support of local governments to address the challenges they are facing due to climate change. This work provides a robust framework and a unique ranking methodology to assess local governments' performance in tackling climate change. Utilising standardised annually reported questionnaires, the methodology calculates climate change related indicators, with the view of better understanding their performance, monitoring their activities and supporting their decision-making process. 7 different key metrics were created, based on the standardised questionnaire, spanning from governance related information to GHG-emissions city-wide levels. Results from this methodology are presented under the scope of supporting local governments to draw conclusions, compare and analyse actions other cities have taken when facing similar challenges, as the yearly reporting process encourages cities and regions to better understand and reflect on the climate risks they face.

Keywords: Climate change, decision support, data-driven, policymaking, indicators, ranking methodology

1 Introduction

Tackling climate change is a multidisciplinary process, which affects all aspects of government, on a local, regional and national scale. The abundance of data available can offer invaluable support to decision makers and governing bodies, as they bring a wealth of information and can be utilised for data-driven and evidence-based actions. However, the availability of data has its own challenges, from capturing the data to the actual value that data-driven services can offer given the multidisciplinary con-

text. As the trend toward data-driven urban climate governance incentivises local city governments to prioritise narrowed metrics and external interests, it inhibits the broader transformations required to realise climate change goals [1].

Actions to address climate change are now widespread as decision-makers prepare for its impacts on areas such as transportation, water supply, public health and infrastructure, utilising data-driven approaches [2], [3], [4]. At the same time, the demand for climate data and services that can contribute to further understanding of the situation and finding the most effective measures to deal. Local governments are now publishing and using data (open or private) to support their decision-making processes, with the assessment of their actions produce tangible results from researchers and public organisations for effective and transparent climate change response action [5], [6], [7], [8].

The interrelationship between adaptation and other agendas at the level of both policy-making and practical implementation of actions is apparent and the need to develop collective responses to climate change impacts integrating sectors, spatial scales and temporal scales is emerging [9]. A keyway of monitoring and identifying the causes and effects of climate change is using indicators, as they can provide aggregated information to policymakers, and the importance of dynamic assessment and modification over time, as new adaptation targets are set and/or as intervention actions are monitored and evaluated [10]. There is a strong tendency to use indicators to assess a community's ability to adapt to climate change. In this way, progress can be made in the evaluation of decision-making and therefore in the design of new climate change adaptation policies.

However, a major problem is that some indicators do not show short-term changes that could immediately raise awareness and mobilise governments and citizens. Another problem is the lack of experience in collecting and managing climate data from the agencies involved. These two issues need to be addressed by implementing forecasts and setting long-term goals at an international level and appropriate staffing and training in data analysis technologies respectively. Below, a selected set of methodologies utilising indicators for climate change related actions is presented.

European Green City Index [11], is a study index in which a comparison of 30 major European cities from the same number of countries in terms of their environmental performance and politics is performed. The overall index consists of 8 categories and 30 sub-indicators, of which 16 are quantitative and measure how the city performs environmentally in practice, while the other 14 are qualitative and evaluate the cities' environmental goals.

Integrated Sustainability Monitoring [12] aims is to investigate the sustainable performance between European Union cities and to detect possible interactions between the three aspects of sustainability: economy, ecology and socio-cultural issues of a city. Each aspect is made up of themes such as land, air, education, health, work and infrastructure. Each theme consists of a multitude of indicators. Through a questionnaire and external sources such as the European Observation Network for Territorial Development and Cohesion (ESPON) and cities' websites, data were collected on 87 indicators.

Green City Conceptual Framework [13] presents a green city conceptual framework (IHS-GCCF) and a harmonised method for measuring green city performance over time (GGCPI). The final tool called the global green city performance index (IHS-GGCPI) consists of 25 sub-indicators in the three main categories, society, economy and environment. It is argued that by using the above framework green performance can be measured, targets set, and achievements tracked. The 25 indicators were divided into 8 categories (1 socio-economic and 7 environmental) and 10 experts, members of academia assigned the weights of the parameters that comprised each of them.

It is therefore essential to provide simple and easy tools in support of local governments to address the challenges they are facing due to climate change. In this paper, a unique methodology based on indicators is presented. A transparent way to gather data, through the use of standardised questionnaires, the ability to track the progress each year and the vast network of cities responding to the questions, make available to create a compact framework of participation and draw conclusions from data-driven services based on a large number of cities.

Apart from the introduction, the paper is organised as follows. Section 2 presented the methodology implemented, section 3 the results and discussion, and in section 4 the conclusion and the next steps for future research purposes.

2 Methodology

The methodology for ranking cities aims to assess their ability to address climate change by collecting and normalising data across seven categories: Governance, Climate Change Adaptation, Renewable Energy, Transportation, GHG Emissions, Waste Management, and Water Security. Cities' answers are used to calculate an initial score for each category, which is then normalised to rank cities in comparison to one another. The ranking process aims to encourage data sharing and disclosure to support better decision-making for tackling climate change.

However, the methodology acknowledges that a low score does not necessarily mean a city is not taking sufficient action, as it is determined by the overall number of cities that responded to the questionnaire and considers the information provided in the questionnaires; not the actions themselves. The indices and scores for each category are created using a combination of quantitative and qualitative data.

A key aspect of the methodology is to raise awareness among cities and local governments that open data initiatives can help optimise resource allocation for addressing climate change. The methodology also provides a simple and effective measurement by processing complex data to produce a single score for each category.

2.1 Data Availability and processing

The main data source used for this methodology is derived from the CDP-ICLEI Track [14], a platform for city climate reporting based on annual questionnaires. ICLEI - Local Governments for Sustainability - is an international, non-governmental organisation that promotes urban sustainable development. Its aim is to support local

and regional governments in achieving their sustainability goals. In 2022, over 2500 cities, counties and associations of local and regional governments from 126 different countries are part of the ICLEI network.

The data used for this paper comes in the form of the annual CDP-ICLEI Unified Common Reporting System questionnaire, which includes information related to several climate change adaptation and mitigation action at the local government level. The data are based on a considerable number of cities in comparison with the other methodologies cited (e.g., the European Green City Index encompasses 30 major European cities while the CDP-ICLEI Track is based on data reported from more than 250 municipalities in 33 countries between 2019 and 2021). The questionnaire is also adapted annually, with new questions added while others are removed, according to the current reality (e.g. in 2021, questions on the impact of the covid-19 pandemic on cities' actions to combat climate change were included in the questionnaire). Furthermore, the questionnaire follows the Common Reporting Framework for GHG Emissions, and its guidelines established by the UNFCCC [15] aiming to facilitate the collection, analysis, and transparency of emissions data, thereby supporting global efforts to mitigate climate change and assess progress towards climate goals.

The questionnaire is structured as follows. For 2021, 133 questions split into 15 different categories are given to local governments. The following table presents the categories, the number of questions included in each one, and the number of questions used for the metrics creation. Apart from the introduction, these are:

Table 1. Questions per category and questions used for the metrics

Category	# questions	# questions included	Category	# questions	# questions included
Waste	7	3	Local Government Emissions	14	8
Governance and Data Management	9	3	Climate Hazards and Vulnerability	12	7
Energy	8	5	Buildings	2	2
City-wide Emissions	21	11	Emissions Reduction	15	5
Adaptation	9	6	Urban Planning	2	1
Transport	13	4	Water Security	7	4
Opportunities	15	4	Food	8	2

The questions are either multiple-choice or open-ended. In the first case the answers are alphanumeric and come from a limited set of possible answers while in the second they are either numerical or alphanumeric. The use of data from open-ended questions that required a written, lengthy response has been avoided in the methodology and emphasis is placed on numerical responses and responses to multiple-choice questions. It is observed, after all, that respondents tend to answer a greater

percentage of multiple-choice questions. Each of the questions can have one or more sub-questions to complete.

The datasets with the local governments' responses to the questionnaire are available online [16], with a sample size of 258 European cities reporting between 2019 and 2021 used for this paper analysis.

A sample of the questions included in the questionnaire are “*Has a climate change risk and vulnerability assessment been undertaken for your city?*”, “*Please provide a breakdown of your GHG emissions by scope. Where values are not available, indicate the reason why.*”, “*Please indicate the source mix of thermal energy (heating and cooling) consumed in your city.*”, “*Does your city collaborate in partnership with businesses and/or industries in your city on sustainability projects?*”

2.2 Metrics

The selection of metrics to create the methodology is based on the questionnaires' structure and its intricacies. The questionnaires evolve over the years, as new information is being requested or questions are being retracted. This leads to the need to process the information within and combine questions for the methodology to be comparable each year as much as possible. Furthermore, it has been noticed that a lot of questions are not being answered (providing answers is not mandatory by the local governments), and this affects the representation that each city will have in the methodology. Based on this constraints, seven different metrics were considered, in line with the questionnaire structure, in order to provide familiarity to its intended audience (i.e., local governments member, filling the questionnaire). As the questionnaires are evolving, further categories can be considered as they seem fit.

The selection of the questions that would be used as indicators and would make up the metrics based on both the categorisation given by ICLEI questionnaires and considered critical, i.e., the possibility of elimination from future questionnaires is minimal. These are questions that provide essential information regarding the present situation in which a local government is, and the awareness it shows on climate issues through its activities and the attempt to take appropriate measures to deal with them.

In each metric, a combination of questions was used in order to provide a single score. The scores in each metric are normalised in the range [0.1], as the intend is to demonstrate the relative performance between local governments, rather than an objective score. This was chosen, given the constraints that assessing performance on absolute levels is not measurable (i.e., there is no perfect score in policy-making, but achievements of successful policies) and that this ranking process aimed to provide a comparison analysis between local governments, for an eventual knowledge-transfer, successful policies implementation and good practices replications.

The metrics considered, along with a description of the information contained by the questions, are the following (based on 2021 questionnaires, as 2022 results are not available at the time of writing):

- **Governance metric**, using indices that measure a city's activities and abilities to address climate change through internal infrastructure and resource allocation. It

considers factors such as strategic decisions for sustainability, joint initiatives, opportunities for local governments to combat climate change, and the support and cooperation of local companies.

- **Climate change adaptation metric**, using indices that measure cities' activities and abilities to address climate hazards they are or will be facing. This metric takes into account the identification of these hazards, corresponding adaptation actions, risk assessment for health issues, and factors that challenge or support the ability to adapt.
- **Renewable energy metric**, using indices that assess cities' activities and abilities to promote clean energy within their boundaries. This metric considers relevant actions taken to support the increase of renewable energy capacity, as well as the percentage of clean energy use within their electricity mix in current or future target years.
- **Transportation metric**, using indices that measure cities' activities and abilities to promote the use of public transportation and low-emission transportation systems. This metric considers factors such as the amount of transit used each year for different means of transportation, availability of charging spots, and air quality information.
- **GHG emissions metric**, using indices which evaluate city response to effective greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions measuring, monitoring, reporting and verification processes. It evaluates the emissions inventory quality, under defined methodologies and covering representative sources of emissions. In addition, it assesses the relevance and impact of cities GHG emissions reduction targets in alignment to the Paris Agreement.
- **Waste management metric**, using indices that assess cities' activities and abilities to ensure safe and secure waste disposal. This metric considers factors such as per capita waste disposal, regulations, initiatives and legislation followed for safe disposal, the type of disposal activities, and the amount of recycling material.
- **Water security metric**, using indices that measure cities' activities and abilities to assess the access and security of clean water for their inhabitants. This metric considers factors such as clean water access and strategic plans for water management, factors and hazards affecting water security in the future, and corresponding adaptation actions.

2.3 Ranking process

A final cumulative score is given to each city, based on the metrics as defined above, to provide the ability of a unified score considering all the metrics. Since each metric contains a different number of questions to calculate their score, the weighted average of each metric is selected. This also provides the ability to choose the importance of each metric by changing the weights, to consider the varying degrees of importance of each metric, if needed.

Each metric is normalised in the [0,1] range by applying the following formula, as suggested from similar approaches [17], [18].

$$X_{normalised} = \frac{X_{actual} - X_{min}}{X_{max} - X_{min}} \quad (1)$$

The total metric is then calculated as the weighted, normalised sum of the individual metrics, where w is the given weight to each metric.

$$X_{total_metric} = \sum w_i * x_{normalised} \quad (2)$$

3 Results and discussion

Applying the methodology for the 2021 questionnaire, the following figure provide the highest ranked cities for the GHG emissions metric as an example.

Fig. 1. Top 10 cities in GHG emissions metric.

The results for the top 10 cities for each metric in descending order are displayed in the following table:

Table 2. Top 10 cities per metric

Emis-sions	Cli-mat. Adapt.	Renewa-ble	Water mgmt.	Waste mgmt.	Transpor-tation	Govern-ance
Berlin	Nice	Copenha-gen	Oslo	Rotter-dam	Copenha-gen	Guimarães
Dijon	Torino	Oslo	West Mid-lands	Barcelona	Berlin	Mann-heim
London	Paris	Turku	Viseu	Paris	Heidelberg	Águeda
Uppsala	Águeda	Uppsala	Paris	Lisbon	Stockholm	Paris
Umeå	Athens	Malmö	Örebro	Milan	Barcelona	Barcelona

Paris	Milan	Somerset	Nice	London	Paris	Bristol
Ljubljana	Braga	Elsinore	Zaragoza	Berlin	Lisbon	Braga
Nice	Glad-saxe	Nyon	Trelleborg	Copenhagen	Rotterdam	Athens
Espoo	Barcelona	Paris	Barcelona	Venice	Venice	Espoo
Lund	Ferrara	Stockholm	Cascais	Stockholm	Helsinki	Nottingham

The results and the scoring of each city is consistent with the findings from other methodologies, as shown in the following table. Below, the results are presented considering equal weights, w_i of (2), for our methodology, in order to compare it with the other indicators, as they don't include weight selection. However, the weights can be changed according to the need of its user, given the fact that some metrics can be considered of higher importance to compared to others.

Table 3. Comparison between different indicators methodologies

Ranking	Total Metric	Green Index	Integrated Sustainability Monitoring	Smart City Index
1	Paris	Copenhagen	Stockholm	Helsinki
2	Barcelona	Stockholm	Munich	Zurich
3	Nice Cote d'Azur	Oslo	Espoo	Oslo
4	Copenhagen	Vienna	Helsinki	Copenhagen
5	Berlin	Amsterdam	Copenhagen	Geneva
6	Oslo	Zurich	Tampere	Amsterdam
7	London	Helsinki	Amsterdam	Munich
8	Elsinore	Berlin	Vienna	Dusseldorf
9	Stockholm	Brussels	Frankfurt	London
10	Milan	Paris	Nijmegen	Stockholm

To draw concrete conclusions from the comparison between the different indices, all the proposed methodologies should have included the same cities as samples. As this is not the case, it can be noticed that all the methodologies have identified as the top cities in the respective indices, cities from north-western Europe. This can be due to the fact that local governments that are located in countries with high GDP can usually be more advanced in the climate change tackling actions, due to higher resources to combat both climate change, but also in the reporting process.

4 Conclusions and next steps

The present work provides a framework and a unique methodology to assess local governments' performance in tackling climate change. The framework derives from

the standardised reporting system managed by ICLEI in combination with CDP, in which annually local governments members of ICLEI network, respond to the questionnaire. The yearly reporting process encourages cities and regions to better understand and reflect on the climate risks they face. Reporting also helps them to embed climate action planning in policymaking and spending, and motivates them to create comprehensive action plans, as well as effective monitoring them.

Utilising this questionnaire, 7 different key metrics were created, by combining a set of selected questions, spanning from Governance to GHG-emissions. The score in each metric was normalised between 0 and 1, to provide the ability of direct comparisons and to create a total metric, incorporating each unique metric, using weighted averages. The adoption of this formula was decided, due to the fact that cities are not required to provide complete responses to the questionnaires, thus not allowing to have questions answered.

The results of the methodology are in agreement with the literature and are predicted to be even more effective if the number of participants increases, as well as the quality of the data. The small number of participants is a problem that can be easier to mitigate, as by providing added value from the use of their data, local governments could be more willing to put effort in the process. The problem behind the unanswered questions cannot be ascertained with certainty. One possibility is that participants find the questionnaire bulky and skip those questions requiring extensive analysis. Replacing all “free-text” questions with multiple choice questions, would make it easier for participants to respond, but this require good planning of the questionnaire. The more likely scenario, however, is that most of the local governments have neither the information nor the means required to provide the requested data. This in turn indicates either a lack of interest in some areas or a lack of resources to strengthen the human and technical potential required to answer the questions validly and fully.

Next steps of this work will consider the further development of the methodology, incorporating annually the new responses in the questionnaires, as well as putting into action the methodology for more direct services in “production” mode, i.e., the use of it by local governments to support them in decision-making processes. This can happen with enhanced data-driven services, such as utilising the methodology and the ranking process to find similarities between cities, in both challenges and solutions, and recommendation of best practices. By having the ability to be informed in a user-friendly way of other local governments’ successful actions to tackle climate change, it will motivate decision makers to adopt similar measures and/or identify gaps or opportunities in their own impact area.

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